

Supplementary Information File 3: Linear Mixed Models Results

EEG Data

The linear mixed model showed no significant main effect of session, $F(1, 38) < 0.01$, $p = .969$, $\eta^2_p < .01$, or movement condition, $F(1, 38) = 0.25$, $p = .617$, $\eta^2_p < .01$. The Session \times Movement Condition interaction was also nonsignificant, $F(1, 38) = 0.36$, $p = .554$, $\eta^2_p < .01$. Overall, the results indicated that the amplitude of neural responses at metre frequencies were not enhanced after vs. before the movement session.

Behavioural Data

Pre- and Post-Movement Sessions

The linear mixed model showed a significant main effect of session, $F(1, 38) = 13.43$, $p < .001$, $\eta^2_p = .26$, with larger $\bar{z}_{\text{clapping}}$ after ($M = 0.49$, $SD = 0.67$) when compared to before the movement ($M = 0.13$, $SD = 0.71$, $d = 0.82$). Note that the effect size is larger than the required SESOI (see Table 1), which indicated that the effect is sufficiently strong to be considered meaningful. The main effect of movement condition was nonsignificant, $F(1, 38) = 0.57$, $p = .455$, $\eta^2_p = .01$. The Session \times Movement Condition interaction was also nonsignificant, $F(1, 38) = 0.45$, $p = .505$, $\eta^2_p = .01$. Overall, the results indicated that the amplitude of metre frequencies was selectively enhanced in the clapping responses after the movement session, similarly for both metrical interpretations (whether culturally congruent or not) that were cued during the body-movement session.

Learning Accuracy

The linear model performed on the hand clapping responses did not show a significant main effect of condition, $F(1, 38) = 2.94$, $p < .094$, $\eta^2_p = .07$. Similarly, the linear model performed on the stepping responses did not show a significant main effect of condition, $F(1, 35) = 0.27$, $p < .606$, $\eta^2_p = .01$. Overall, these results indicated that the clapping and stepping accuracy were not significantly different between the two metrical interpretations that were cued during the body-movement session.

Head Movements

The linear mixed model showed no significant main effect of session, $F(1, 76) = 1.28$, $p = .261$, $\eta^2_p = .02$, or movement condition, $F(1, 76) = 0.04$, $p = .847$, $\eta^2_p < .01$. The Session \times Movement Condition interaction was also nonsignificant, $F(1, 76) = 0.56$, $p = .559$, $\eta^2_p < .01$. Overall, the results indicated that periodic head movements were not (a) enhanced after vs. before the movement session and (b) different between experimental conditions.